

Construction of an individual model for estimating blood pressure using independent components of facial skin temperature considering time variation

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Abstract: The objective of this study was to construct an individual model for estimating blood pressure (BP) using independent components of facial skin temperature considering time variation. In our previous study, an individual model was constructed for estimating BP by applying independent component analysis to facial skin temperature of each subject. However, in this previous study, time variations in facial skin temperature were not considered. Facial skin temperature is assumed to be related to blood flow over time as blood helps in transporting heat in the body. Therefore, the accuracy of the BP estimation model can be expected to improve if the variation of facial skin temperature caused by blood flow over time considered in addition to only the facial skin temperature. Consequently, the accuracy of the proposed model with the aforementioned considerations was found to be better than that of without these considerations. Therefore, the BP was accurately estimated using the proposed approach.

Keywords: Blood pressure, Facial thermal image; Independent component analysis; Noncontact measurement

I. INTRODUCTION

Timely detection of hypertension requires continuous monitoring of blood pressure (BP) in daily life [1-2]. The conventional method of measuring BP involves the use of sphygmomanometers, which work by elevating and lowering the pressure inside a rubber cuff and are generally worn on the arm or middle finger [3]. This method, however, is unsuitable for continuously monitoring BP in daily life because it necessitates constant body contact. Hence, noncontact BP measurement techniques are necessary to achieve continuous BP monitoring [4]. Facial skin temperature as a method of noncontact BP measurement was focus of this study. The facial skin temperature was measured using a thermographic device. Our previous study attempted to construct an individual model for estimating BP by applying independent component analysis (ICA) algorithms, which are a type of blind source separate algorithms, used to extract components related to BP [5]. The model, however, was constructed based only on facial skin temperature during variation of BP. However, the variation of BP depends on blood flow and energy required to pump blood from the heart over time, and the heat generated by blood [6-7]. Another previous study of ours revealed the different

facial skin temperature distribution owing to variation in BP [8]. Therefore, the model for estimating BP must be constructed using not only the variation of facial skin temperature but also the variation of facial skin temperature caused by blood flow over time.

In line with the objective of this study was to construct an individual model for estimating BP using independent components of facial skin temperature in consideration of time variation. ICA was, thereafter, applied to it in order to extract independent components of BP. A model for estimating BP was constructed using differentials and second differentials of these components as time variation of facial skin temperature. Models with and without time variation of facial skin temperature were subsequently compared.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Experimental system

The physiological indices considered were: facial skin temperature and, mean blood pressure (MBP). The bioinstrumentation system comprised an infrared thermography device (TVS-200EX; Avionics CO., Ltd) and non-invasive blood continuous hemodynamometer (Finometer MIDI; Finapres Medical Systems, the

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Netherlands). The infrared thermography device was set up at a distance of 120 cm from the subjects' face. Thermal images were created at 1-s sampling intervals. The size of each thermal image was 640×480 pixels, and the temperature resolution was less than 0.05°C . The infrared emissivity of skin was $\varepsilon = 0.98$. The hemodynamic parameters were measured by attaching a BP cuff to the second joint of the left middle finger with a hemodynamometer operating at 1Hz.

B. Procedure and condition

Seven healthy young people [five male and two female: aged, 21.4 ± 0.5 years (Mean \pm S.D.)] participated in the experiments and conducted in the experimental room. The subjects were fully informed about the experiment and the objectives of this study prior to participation, and were asked to signed a consent form. The experiment was conducted in an experiment room with a temperature set to $25.7 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The measurements began after the subjects had been in the room for at least 15 min to acclimatize them to the room temperature. The experiment comprised four 1-min resting state segments, and three 30-s Valsalva segments. In each Valsalva segment, the subjects held their breath to cause variation of BP. They repeatedly conducted and the entire experiment was conducted while the subjects were seated with their eyes closed.

III. ANALYSIS METHOD

A. Independent component analysis

In the simplest form of ICA, we observe m scalar random variables, that is, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m . These are assumed to be linear combinations of n independent components, denoted by s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n . We arrange the observed variables x_k into a vector $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}_k(t)^T (k = 1, 2, \dots, m, m \geq t)$ and the component variables s_i into a vector $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{s}_i(m)^T (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$. The linear relationship is given by ICA is a statistical analysis that estimates independent components \mathbf{S} from observed signal by assuming independent component \mathbf{A} , which are mutually independent. ICA was computed using the following formula

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{AS} = [\mathbf{A}_1, \mathbf{A}_2, \dots, \mathbf{A}_t]^T [\mathbf{S}_1, \mathbf{S}_2, \dots, \mathbf{S}_n] \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} , is called the weighting matrix, which is an unknown $t \times n$ matrix of full column rank. The

independent components are assumed to be mutually independent and have zero means. The basic challenged faced by ICA is the estimation of both the weighting matrix \mathbf{A} and the independent components $s_i(m)$ using only the observed mixture signals $x_k(t)$.

B. Construction of an individual model for estimating BP

The facial thermal image (FTI) containing no background or subject's hair, was cropped from the thermal image. The FTI included the forehead, lip, and cheek regions and was centered on the nasal region. An example of the same is shown Fig. 1. The FTIs were downsampled with an average of 2×2 pixels. Each downsampled FTI was filtered using 0.1 Hz of a low-pass filter to remove temperature fluctuations due to imperceptible facial movements during the time of measurements. The FTIs were transformed into the one-dimensional vector:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = [x_1(t), x_2(t), x_3(t), \dots, x_a(t)] \quad (2)$$

The time-series of FTI vector was represented in the form of the following matrix

$$\mathbf{X}_{FTI} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{1,1} & \dots & x_{1,a} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{t,1} & \dots & x_{t,a} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $x_{t,a}$ represents FTI components of the pixel a at time t s. The \mathbf{X}_{FTI} was applied to ICA and weighting matrix, \mathbf{A} , and independent components, \mathbf{S} , were estimated using following formula.

$$\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}(1), \mathbf{a}(2), \dots, \mathbf{a}(t)]^T = \begin{bmatrix} a_{1,1} & \dots & a_{1,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{t,1} & \dots & a_{t,n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{S} = [\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \dots, \mathbf{s}_n]^T = \begin{bmatrix} s_{1,1} & \dots & s_{1,a} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ s_{n,1} & \dots & s_{n,a} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{S} reveals the feature quantities based on a specific facial region by \mathbf{s}_n , and \mathbf{a}_n , which is called the index weighting, indicates the contribution of \mathbf{s}_n to \mathbf{X}_{FTI} . Fig. 2 shows an example of the \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{A} . The \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{A} graph represent images of independent components and the corresponding temporal change in \mathbf{A} . The horizontal axis and vertical axis indicate the time and weighting values, respectively. The red and

Fig. 1. Example of an FTI extracted from a thermal image

Fig. 2. Example of independent components, S , and corresponding weighting variation, A .

blue colors signify strong and weak features, respectively. In this study, we used the fast_ICA algorithm, which is known to be fast and converges successfully [9-10]. The number of independent components, n , is determined by the total contribution of the principal components. The principal components, arranged in descending order, whose contribution was 95 % , were used [11]. The time-series data of MBP and A was filtered using a moving-average-filter of 10 s. The A , differential A' , and second differential, A'' were calculated using filtered A to consider the time variation of the facial skin temperature using the following formula

$$A' = [a'_1, a'_2, \dots, a'_n] = [a_2 - a_1, \dots, a_{n-1} - a_n] \quad (6)$$

$$A'' = [a''_1, a''_2, \dots, a''_n] \\ = [a'_2 - a'_1, \dots, a'_{n-1} - a'_n] \quad (7)$$

The A' and A'' were filtered to 0.1 Hz of low-pass filter in order to smoothen their values. The explanatory variable was filtered MBP, and the objective variable were the A , A' and A'' during all experiments. A multiple regression analysis was performed to construction an individual model for estimating BP. Individual models for estimating BP using just the A and all of the A , A' and A'' were constructed, and both models were compared.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The individual model for estimating BP using each subject's weighting matrix in Sub. A-G was constructed. Table 1 presents the results of comparison between model using A and model using A , A' and A'' and the number of variables in the model using A , A' and A'' . The root mean square error (RMSE) of the model using A and model using A , A' and A'' were 5.12 ± 1.18 mmHg and 3.91 ± 0.38 mmHg (*Mean*±*S.D.*), respectively. The accuracy of model using A , A' and A'' was better than model using A . Moreover, the A , A' and A'' were selected as variables related to MBP in the individual model considering time variation. Fig. 3 shows the result of the mean error of the model using A and the model using A , A' and A'' . The horizontal axis indicates each segment and the vertical axis indicates mean error of MBP during each segment in all subjects. The baseline indicates no error, and the error bars indicate the standard error. The results represented in Fig. 3 show that accuracy of the model using A , A' and A'' in both Rest and Valsalva segments was better than the model using A , and the model using A , A' and A'' can estimate during any sharp change in MBP of Valsalva.

As one of the factors for the improvement of accuracy of the model, first and second differential of weighting value was suggested to be extracted which were the components related to amount of blood flow and power to pump blood from the heart over time. From those, it was demonstrated that the accuracy of the model for estimating BP improved considering time variation of facial skin temperature as amount of blood flow and energy to pump blood from the heart over time.

V. CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to construct an individual model for estimating BP using independent components of facial skin temperature considering time variation. An individual model for estimating BP was constructed using none, first and second differential of independent components of facial skin temperature. The individual model with and without time variation of facial skin temperature were compared. As a result, the RMSE of the individual model without and with time variation of facial skin temperature were 5.12 ± 1.18 mmHg and 3.91 ± 0.38 mmHg (*Mean*±*S.D.*), respectively. This revealed that the accuracy of the

Table 1. Results of comparison between model using A and model using A , A' and A'' and the number of variations in model using A , A' and A''

Subject	RMSE [mmHg]		Number of (A , A' , A'')
	A	A , A' and A''	
A	4.55	3.87	5,4,4
B	3.78	3.21	3,4,3
C	5.20	3.63	3,3,1
D	5.99	4.40	3,7,4
E	4.26	3.92	2,5,7
F	7.52	4.00	2,3,3
G	4.57	4.34	7,5,5

Fig. 3. Results of the mean error of the model using A and the model using A , A' and A''

model for estimating BP using variation of facial skin temperature over time was better than the model without it. It was therefore found that the proposed individual model was able to estimate BP.

In a future study, additional subjects will be included for the construction of a more robust model for estimation BP. We also plan to construct a general model for estimating BP, which is a simplex model for estimating BP from facial skin temperatures of any given person.

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